

Ecological Attitude of Post Graduate Girl Students in West Bengal

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Abstract

Ecology is the study of the relationships between organisms and their environment. It encompasses the interactions between living organism and the physical and biological components of their environment, including the interactions among species as well as the flow of energy and nutrients through ecosystems. Ecology considers organism at the individual, population, community, ecosystem and biosphere levels. Ecological attitudes are related to ecological issues and problems. With the help of proper interaction between environment and human beings we can maintain environmental equilibrium. The present study is an attempt to know the ecological attitude of Post Graduate Girls students. For this purpose the researcher used Descriptive Survey method. In this research work the population is all Post Graduate Girl Students of West Bengal in India. In the present study, the researcher selected total 105 Post Graduate Girl Students (Urban & Rural) using stratified simple random sampling method. For the collection of data Ecological Attitude and Cognitive Scale (EACS) developed by Rajamanickam was used. From the result it is found that there is significant difference between Urban & Rural Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude. It is also found that there is significant difference between Science & Arts Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude. The finding of the present study shows that there is significant positive relationship among four sub-scales of Ecological Attitude which are Oral Obligation, Real Obligation, Emotional Obligation, and Cognitive Obligation.

Keywords

Ecology, Ecological Attitude, Environment, Post Graduate Girl Students

Introduction

Education is the key to a better life. Education is not only a means of knowledge transmission but also a platform for developing values, attitudes, and behaviours that support sustainable living. In the 21st century, education plays a crucial role not only in academic development but also in shaping an individual's attitudes toward pressing global issues such as environmental sustainability. And also it is widely recognized as a critical factor influencing an individual's social and economic success, as it provides a path way to improved opportunities and a better quality of life.

Ecology is the study of the relationships between living organisms and their physical environment. It examines how organisms interact with each other and their environment at various levels, including the individual, population, community, ecosystem, and biosphere. The health of each person and society testifies to the viability and range of adaptive capabilities to changing environmental conditions. Social health depends on the degree of danger of the conditions that society itself creates. Ecology is one criterion that ensures the level of social health. Social health is dependent on culturally accepted values such as kindness, respect, and fruitful relationships. The reflection of biological, psychological, and cultural features in specific conditions is under the social health of a population. As a result, each person and society develops an ecological attitude and ecological motivation to interact with nature, which characterizes the level of social health. Ecology can help us understand how to improve the environment, Manage natural resources, and Protect human health. Ecological attitude is a person's collection of beliefs, feelings, and intentions about environmental issues and activities. It's a psychological tendency that can be expressed as favor or disfavor of the natural environment. Ecological attitudes can be important because they often determine how a person's behavior affects the environment. For example, people with more favorable attitudes towards the environment are more likely to act in ways that help the environment. Some factors that can affect a person's ecological attitude are age, gender, socioeconomic status, nation, urban-rural residence, religion, politics, values, personality, and experience.

Ecology is a functional unit of nature where organisms always live as a community and interact with each other with its surrounding environment. This structural and functional system of community and environment is ecosystem. Today, various human activities are causing ecological crisis and creating a situation of natural imbalance. Ecological and environmental attitudes are beliefs or values about given environmental issues. Environmental issues include environmental degradation, air and water pollution, radioactive pollution, green house effect, global warming, interrelationship between

environment and society, impact of economic growth and technology on the environment and many other environmental problems. In short, ecological approach is related to ecological problems. Environmental values, society's attitude and relationship towards the environment, all affect the environmental balance. Keeping this perspective in mind, the related study was conducted.

In recent decades, global concerns about environmental sustainability have significantly increased. Human being and any other organisms are a part of environment and completely dependent on this environment. They fulfil their basic necessities like food, water, air and shelter from environment. But in the present World, environmental issues like climate change, global warming, sea water level rise, pollution are the most essential problems of the earth. It is the effect of unawareness and harmful activity of human beings and indirect economical growth as to negative effect on environment and ecosystem. So the environmental issues are the emergious topical over the world and have to take right action to protect our planet because we are the responsible for this. This is the right time to cultivate environmental awareness and environmental sensitivity among youths. It is very necessary to comprise the ecology as a compulsory subject in the curriculum at each level to secure environmental awareness at various disciplines.

Ecology is "a biological science of which deal with complex interactions among organism and between organism and their environment." It forms the heart and soul of the environmental science. The term "Ecology" was coined by Ernst Haeckel in 1869. It is derived from the Greek words 'Oikos'- home and 'Logos'- study. Ecology deals with the study of organisms in their natural home interacting with their surroundings. The surroundings or environment consists of living organisms (biotic) and physical (abiotic) components. Modern ecologists believe that an adequate definition of ecology must specify some unit of study and one such basic unit described by Tansley (1935) was ecosystem. According to other definition-an ecosystem is a self-regulating group of biotic communities of species interacting with one another and with their non-living environment exchanging energy and matter. Now ecology is often defined as "the study of ecosystems."

According to Charles J. Krebs (1972) – "Ecology is the scientific study of interactions that determine the distribution and abundance of organisms."

Objective of study

The objectives of the study are as follows:

1. To study the significant difference between Urban & Rural Post Graduate Girl Students;
2. To study the significant difference between Science & Arts Post Graduate Girl Students;
3. To study the significant relationship among four sub-scales of Ecological Attitude which are Oral Obligation, Real Obligation, Emotional Obligation, and Cognitive Obligation.

Hypotheses of the Study

H₀₁ : There would be no significant difference between Urban & Rural Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude;

H₀₂: There would be no significant difference between Urban & Rural Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Oral Obligation sub-scale;

H₀₃ : There would be no significant difference between Urban & Rural Girls Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Real Obligation sub-scale;

H₀₄ : There would be no significant difference between Urban & Rural Girls Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Emotional Obligation sub-scale;

H₀₅ : There would be no significant difference between Urban & Rural Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Cognitive Obligation sub-scale;

H₀₆: There would be no significant difference between Science & Arts Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude;

H₀₇ : There would be no significant difference between Science & Arts Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Oral Obligation sub-scale;

H₀₈ : There would be no significant difference between Science & Arts Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Real Obligation sub-scale;

H₀₉ : There would be no significant difference between Science & Arts Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Emotional Obligation sub-scale;

H_{010} : There would be no significant difference between Science & Arts Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Cognitive Obligation sub-scale;

H_{011} : There would be no significant relationship among four sub-scales of Ecological Attitude which are Oral Obligation, Real Obligation, Emotional Obligation, and Cognitive Obligation.

Review of Literature

Sayeh et al. (2025) found that students' environmental attitudes are shaped by their academic backgrounds and personal experiences. Banerjee & Singh. (2024) conducted research entitled "**A Study on the Relationship between Pro-Environmental Behaviour and Environmental Attitude of Secondary School Students of Kolkata.**" The study revealed that there are no significant differences among male and female students regarding level of pro-environmental behaviour and environmental attitude and also there is a significant relationship between pro-environmental behaviour and environmental attitude. Badoni & Badola. (2024) researched on "**Study of Ecological Attitude of Senior Secondary Level Boys and Girls Students of Tehri and Pauri Garhwal Districts of Uttarakhand.**" The result revealed girls students have significantly high awareness about Environment in comparison to boys students. Roy (2023) had conducted the research work entitled "**Pro-environmental attitude of college students of India and Bangladesh.**" Results revealed that due to rapid globalization, land distribution, and land reform, the lack of proper planning by the government and others' perceptions are hampered. This study also suggests some environmental programs where students could participate in the decision-making process in order to conserve the environment and shows the area for future research. Badoni (2017) researched on "**Comparative study of Ecological Attitude of Rural and Urban Senior Secondary School Students.**" It was shown that there was significant difference between rural and urban senior secondary students of Tehri district on different dimensions of ecological attitude and cognitive scale. It was also shown that there was significant variation between rural and urban senior secondary students. Kirmani (2016) studied a research work on "**Environmental Concern to Attitude towards Green Products: Evidences from India.**" The study findings indicate that environmental concern has a significant and positive influence on attitude towards green products.

Qadri, et, al., (2025) had conducted a research entitled "**Wealth, Wisdom and the will to Protect: An Examination of Socio-Economic Influences on Environment.**" The result revealed that education is a consistently strong predictor of Pro- environmental attitudes. Vrselja, et, al., (2024) had conducted a research work under the title "**Relationship between Socioeconomic status and Pro-Environmental Behaviour: The Role of Efficacy Beliefs.**" The result revealed that the socio-economic status had no direct effect on Pro- environmental behaviour self-efficacy and collective efficacy was associated with Pro- environmental behaviour. Vinke. (2024) had conducted a research entitled "**Socioeconomic Status and Environmental Behaviour: A Reflexive Thematic Analysis.**" It was found that the higher groups see environmental behaviour as a way of financial investment to regain their money, while not investing time and efforts and lower groups see sustainability as an investment in time and comfort, being deficient in financial resource. Sowmya and Sharath (2023) researched on "**A Study on Environmental Attitude among Secondary School Students of Mysore District.**" The analysis of data revealed that there was no significant difference between Boys and Girls of secondary school students towards Environmental attitude, as well as locality. Whereas no significant difference between Urban and Rural secondary school students with respect to Environmental attitude. Somashekara and Praveena (2021) had conducted research work under the title "**A Comparative Study on the Environmental Attitude and Ecological Behavior among the Postgraduate Students.**" Based on the analyses and findings the study concluded that there was a significance difference between Arts and Science Post graduate students of university of Mysore with respect to their Environmental attitude. There was no significant difference between Arts and Science Post graduate students of university of Mysore with respect to their Ecological behavior. It was found that there is a positive low correlation between Environmental attitude and Ecological behavior arts and science Post graduate students of university of Mysore. Florian et al. (1999) carried out a research work on "**Ecological Behavior, Environmental Attitude, and Feelings of Responsibility for the Environment.**" The finding revealed that Ecological Behavior Intention could be predicted more accurately by adding Responsibility Feelings into the rather general environmental attitude approach.

Research Gap

Although lots of research has been done in India and foreign countries on the variables Ecological Attitude but limited studies compares Ecological Attitude across different disciplines (e.g., Science vs Arts). Most studies examine general student population; specific insights into Post Graduate Girl Students' ecological attitudes and behaviour are lacking. This underscores significant research gap in understanding the ecological attitude.

Main Text

Definition of the terms used in the Study

Ecological Attitude

Ecology is the study of the relationships between living organisms, including humans, and their physical environment. Ecological attitude refers to a person's beliefs, feelings, and behavioural tendencies toward the environment and ecological issues. It reflects how

much someone values nature and is willing to act to protect it. It is a psychological tendency that influences how people perceive and evaluate the natural world, and their likelihood to engage in environmentally-friendly behaviours. Ecological attitudes are related to ecological issues and problems. Different anthropogenic activities creates a number of environmental problems like pollution, soil erosion, green house effect, ozone layer depletion, global warming and degradation of natural resources.

Post Graduate Girl Students

Post Graduate Students are those students who are undergoing two-year Post Graduate course in any educational institute. In the present study 'Post Graduate Girl Students' refers to those Science & Arts girls students of P.G. course in West Bengal.

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of this descriptive survey research is to study the Ecological Attitude of Post Graduate Girl Students. The title of this study is:

“Ecological Attitude of Post Graduate Girl Students in West Bengal.”

Emergence of the Problem

Ecology is the study of the relationships between living organisms, including humans, and their physical environment; it seeks to understand the vital Ecology connections between plants and animals and the world around them. It deals with the study of relationship between biotic and abiotic components. It also provides information about the benefits of ecosystems and how we can use Earth's resources in ways that leave the environment healthy for future generations. Ecology is the study of the interactions between biotic organisms and their environment. Ecological attitudes are related to ecological issues and problems. Different anthropogenic activities creates a number of environmental problems like pollution ,soil erosion, green house effect, ozone layer depletion, global warming and degradation of natural resources. All these human created changes are responsible for global climate change. Increasing urbanization and industrialization creates a number of environmental problems and crises. These activities have disturbed the ecological balance and have resulted in loss of natural resources and extinction of flora and fauna. Therefore environmental equilibrium has to be maintained through environmental awareness and education programs. With the help of proper interaction between environment and human beings we can maintain environmental equilibrium.

Hence, it became relevant to know the ecological attitude. The aim of the researcher is to know the Ecological Attitude of Post Graduate Girl Students.

Modern ecologist Smith(1977) has defined ecology as “A multi disciplinary science which deals with organism and its place to live and focuses on the ecosystem.” In simple term Ecology is the study of interaction between living organisms and their environment and the pattern of distribution of planets and animals on the earth.

Relevance of the Problem

1. Environmental Challenges: West Bengal faces unique environmental issues like pollution and climate impacts, making it crucial to understand students' ecological attitudes for sustainability.
2. Gender Perspective: Focusing on girl students highlights gender-specific influences on environmental awareness and behaviors, which can shape targeted education strategies.
3. Education & Awareness: Understanding their attitudes helps assess the effectiveness of environmental education in shaping sustainable practices among young women.
4. Awareness-Attitude-Action Gap: Identifying gaps between knowledge, attitude, and action can guide interventions to promote sustainable behaviors among this group.
5. Policy & Development: Insights can inform policies and programs fostering environmental responsibility among educated youth, especially women, in West Bengal.

Significance of the Problem

1. Shaping Sustainable Futures: Understanding their attitudes can help develop targeted interventions to promote sustainability and environmental responsibility.
2. Empowering Women: Focusing on girl students highlights the role of educated women in driving environmental change in their communities.
3. Addressing Regional Challenges: West Bengal's unique environmental issues (e.g., pollution, climate impacts) require context-specific solutions informed by students' attitudes.
4. Bridging the Awareness-Action Gap: Insights can help universities and policymakers bridge gaps between environmental awareness, attitudes, and sustainable behaviors.
5. Influencing Policy & Education: Findings can shape environmental education, policies, and programs promoting sustainability among youth in India.

Methodology

Methodology of the Study including Population, Sample, Sampling Technique, Sampling Design, Variables of the Study and Tool used in the Study are described here. This chapter also defines different terms used in the study.

Methodology of the Study

The present study conducted to know the Ecological Attitude of Post Graduate Girl Students. The researcher used Descriptive Survey method for this study.

Population

In this research work the population is all Post Graduate Girl Students of West Bengal.

Sample

In the present study, the researcher selected total 105 Post Graduate Girl Students from four department of Diamond Harbour Women's University of South Twenty Four Parganas, where almost 50% are Science Post Graduate Girl Students & 50% are Arts Post Graduate Girl Students and 38% Post Graduate Girl Students are from Urban area & 62% Post Graduate Girl Students are from Rural area.

Sampling Technique

In the present study, the researcher collected data by using Stratified Random Sampling Method.

Sampling Design

- 1. **Main Variable:** Ecological Attitude
- 2. **Categorical Variables:** Locality, Stream, Sub-scales

Tools Used

The Ecological Attitude and Cognitive Scale (EACS) developed by Rajamanickam (1999). The reliability coefficient is 0.76 and Cronbach's alpha value is 0.83. The EACS is a 40-item scale that measures ecological attitude and cognition across four sub-scales: 1. Oral Obligation Scale: Measures the expression of favorable or unfavorable attitudes toward environmental issues. 2. Real Obligation Scale: Assesses a person's actual practical actions and commitment to solving environmental problems. 3. Emotional Obligation Scale: Determines the degree of feeling an individual expresses when faced with ecological issues. 4. Cognitive

Scale: Intended to assess an individual's knowledge and understanding of ecological problems. It was administered on 20 to 55 years age group.

Analysis

Inferential Statistics

This part deals with the analysis and interpretation by means of inferential statistics i.e. t-test and coefficient of correlation. In the present study, Independent Sample t-test and Pearson Correlation Coefficient is employed using SPSS to analyze the database.

Table 1 : Representing t-value between Ecological Attitude of Urban & Rural Post Graduate Girl Students

H₀₁ There would be no significant difference between Urban & Rural Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude

Locality	No. of Girls Post Graduate Students	Ecological Attitude		df	p value at 0.05 level of significance
		M	S.D		
Urban	40	23.38	5.61	103	0.004
Rural	65	26.23	4.38		

Table 1 shows that the obtained p value is 0.004 which is less than 0.05 at the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, it is significant at the 0.05 level of significance. So the null hypothesis is rejected. It means there is significant difference between Urban & Rural Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude.

Table 2: Representing t-value among Four Sub-scales of Ecological Attitude of Urban & Rural Post Graduate Girl Students

H₀₂ There would be no significant difference between Urban & Rural Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Oral Obligation sub-scale.

H₀₃ There would be no significant difference between Urban & Rural Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Real Obligation sub-scale.

H₀₄ There would be no significant difference between Urban & Rural Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Emotional Obligation sub-scale.

H₀₅ There would be no significant difference between Urban & Rural Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Cognitive Obligation sub-scale.

	Sub-Scales	Area				df	p value at 0.05 level of significance	
		Urban (40)		Rural (65)				
		M	S.D	M	S.D			
Ecological Attitude	Oral Obligation	6.60	1.58	7.26	1.80	103	.058	Not Sig.
	Real Obligation	5.90	1.46	6.62	1.47		.017	Sig.
	Emotional Obligation	6.38	2.27	7.28	1.43		.014	Sig.
	Cognitive Obligation	4.50	1.63	5.08	1.54		.072	Not Sig.

Table2 shows that the obtained p value of four sub-scales of Ecological Attitude is .058, .017, .014 and .072. Hence, it is not significant for Oral Obligation sub-scale and Cognitive Obligation sub-scale at the 0.05 level of significance. It is significant for Real Obligation sub-scale and Emotional Obligation sub-scale at the 0.05 level of significance. So two null hypotheses, H₀₂ & H₀₅ are retained and another two null hypotheses H₀₃ & H₀₄ are rejected.

Table 3: Representing t-value between Ecological Attitude of Science & Arts Post Graduate Girl Students

H₀₆ There would be no significant difference between Science & Arts Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude

Stream	No. of Girls Post Graduate Students	Ecological Attitude		Df	p value at 0.05 level of significance
		M	S.D		
Science	55	28.09	3.92	103	.000
Arts	50	21.90	4.10		

Table 3 shows that the obtained p value is .000 which is less than 0.05 at the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, it is significant at the 0.05 level of significance. So the null hypothesis is rejected. It means there is significant difference between Science & Arts Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude.

Table 4: Representing t-value among Four Sub-scales of Ecological Attitude of Science & Arts Post Graduate Girl Students

H₀₇ There would be no significant difference between Science & Arts Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Oral Obligation sub-scale.

H₀₈ There would be no significant difference between Science & Arts Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Real Obligation sub-scale.

H₀₉ There would be no significant difference between Science & Arts Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Emotional Obligation sub-scale.

H₀₁₀ There would be no significant difference between Science & Arts Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Cognitive Obligation sub-scale.

	Sub-Scales	Stream				df	p value at 0.05 level of significance	
		Science (55)		Arts (50)				
		M	S.D	M	S.D			
Ecological Attitude	Oral Obligation	7.76	1.69	6.18	1.40	103	.000	Sig.
	Real Obligation	6.95	1.42	5.68	1.30		.000	Sig.
	Emotional Obligation	7.87	1.35	5.90	1.76		.000	Sig.
	Cognitive Obligation	5.51	1.59	4.14	1.28		.000	Sig.

Table 4 shows that the obtained p value Science and Arts Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of four sub-scales of Ecological Attitude is .000. Hence, it is significant for all four sub-scales at the 0.05 level of significance. So, four null hypotheses H₀₇ H₀₈ & H₀₉ H₀₁₀ are rejected.

Table 5: Representing coefficient of correlation among four sub-scales of Ecological Attitude of Science & Arts Post Graduate Girl Students

H₀₁₁ There would be no significant relationship among four sub-scales of Ecological Attitude which are Oral Obligation, Real Obligation, Emotional Obligation, and Cognitive Obligation.

	Sub-Scales	No. of Girls Post Graduate Students	Df	Correlation coefficient (r)	Status of Correlation	Table value of r at 0.01 level of significance
Oral Obligation	Real Obligation	105	103	.471	Moderate	.254
	Emotional Obligation			.453	Moderate	
	Cognitive Obligation			.354	Low	
Real Obligation	Oral Obligation			.471		
	Emotional Obligation			.500	Moderate	
	Cognitive Obligation			.382	Low	
Emotional Obligation	Oral Obligation			.453		
	Real Obligation			.500		
	Cognitive Obligation			.412	Moderate	
Cognitive Obligation	Oral Obligation			.354		
	Real Obligation			.382		
	Emotional Obligation			.412		

Table 5 shows the coefficient of correlation among four sub-scales of Ecological Attitude. It is observed the calculated r values are greater than the tabulated value i.e. 0.254 at 0.01 level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. It means there are significant relationships among four sub-scales of Ecological Attitude. From the r value in the table, it is also can be stated that the correlation is positive.

Result and Discussion

From the result it is found that there is significant difference between Urban & Rural Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude. Above result is consistent with the result of previous study performed by Badoni (2017). But the result not supports the results of studies by Sowmya & Sharath (2023). From the result it is found that there is significant difference between Science & Arts Post Graduate Girl Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude. The result not supports the results of studies by Somashekara &

Praveena (2021). According to the relationship, the findings of the present study shows that there is significant positive relationship among four sub-scales of Ecological Attitude which are Oral Obligation, Real Obligation, Emotional Obligation, and Cognitive Obligation which is consistent with the results of studies by Somashekara & Praveena (2021), Kirmani (2016) who found significant positive relationship.

Findings

1. Significant difference has been observed between Urban & Rural Girls Post Graduate Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude. It also observed that mean of Rural Students Ecological Attitude are greater than that of Urban Students Ecological Attitude. That means Rural students have more favourable ecological attitude than Urban students.
2. There would be no significant difference between Urban & Rural Girls Post Graduate Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Oral Obligation sub-scale. That means Urban and Rural Girls Post Graduate students are same in respect of Ecological Attitude with reference to Oral Obligation sub-scale.
3. Significant difference has been observed between Urban & Rural Girls Post Graduate Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Real Obligation sub-scale. It also observed that mean of Rural Students Ecological Attitude with reference to Real Obligation sub-scale are greater than that of Urban Students Ecological Attitude with reference to Real Obligation sub-scale. That means Rural students have more favourable ecological attitude with reference to Real Obligation sub-scale than Urban students.
4. Significant difference has been observed between Urban & Rural Girls Post Graduate Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Emotional Obligation sub-scale. It also observed that mean of Rural Students Ecological Attitude with reference to Emotional Obligation sub-scale are greater than that of Urban Students Ecological Attitude with reference to Emotional Obligation sub-scale. That means Rural students have more favourable ecological attitude with reference to Emotional Obligation sub-scale than Urban students.
5. There is no significant difference between Urban & Rural Girls Post Graduate Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Cognitive Obligation sub-scale. That means Urban and Rural Girls Post Graduate students are same in respect of Ecological Attitude with reference to Cognitive Obligation sub-scale.
6. Significant difference has been observed between Science & Arts Girls Post Graduate Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude. It also observed that mean of Science Girls Post Graduate Students Ecological Attitude are greater than that of Arts Students Ecological Attitude. That means Science students have more favourable ecological attitude than Arts students.
7. Significant difference has been observed between Science & Arts Girls Post Graduate Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Oral Obligation sub-scale. It also observed that mean of Science students Ecological Attitude with reference to Oral Obligation sub-scale are greater than that of Arts Students Ecological Attitude with reference to Oral Obligation sub-scale. That means Science students have more favourable ecological attitude with reference to Oral Obligation sub-scale than Arts students.
8. Significant difference has been observed between Science & Arts Girls Post Graduate Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Real Obligation sub-scale. It also observed that mean of Science students Ecological Attitude with reference to Real Obligation sub-scale are greater than that of Arts Students Ecological Attitude with reference to Real Obligation sub-scale. That means Science students have more favourable ecological attitude with reference to Real Obligation sub-scale than Arts students.
9. Significant difference has been observed between Science & Arts Girls Post Graduate Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Emotional Obligation sub-scale. It also observed that mean of Science students Ecological Attitude with reference to Emotional Obligation sub-scale are greater than that of Arts Students Ecological Attitude with reference to Emotional Obligation sub-scale. That means Science students have more favourable ecological attitude with reference to Emotional Obligation sub-scale than Arts students.
10. Significant difference has been observed between Science & Arts Girls Post Graduate Students on the basis of Ecological Attitude with reference to Cognitive Obligation sub-scale. It also observed that mean of Science students Ecological Attitude with reference to Cognitive Obligation sub-scale are greater than that of Arts Students Ecological Attitude with reference to Cognitive Obligation sub-scale. That means Science students have more favourable ecological attitude with reference to Cognitive Obligation sub-scale than Arts students.
11. There is significant positive relationship among four sub-scales of Ecological Attitude which are Oral Obligation, Real Obligation, Emotional Obligation, and Cognitive Obligation. So, association among four sub-scales of Ecological Attitude which is Oral Obligation, Real Obligation, Emotional Obligation, and Cognitive Obligation exists.

Conclusion

Ecological attitudes can be important because they often determine how a person's behavior affects the environment. For example, people with more favorable attitudes towards the environment are more likely to act in ways that help the environment.

Educational Implications

The Educational implications of the study are as follows:

1. **Environmental Awareness:** Students can learn how their actions and decisions impact the environment. They can also learn how to take action to protect the environment and use natural resources wisely.
2. **Environmental Responsibility:** Students can learn to be responsible for the environment and become stewards of it.
3. **Healthy Lifestyles:** Students can learn how to live healthy lifestyles.
4. **Climate Change Awareness:** Students can learn about climate change and become more aware of it.
5. **Ecological Literacy:** Students can learn about ecological literacy.
6. **Sustainable Lifestyles:** Students can learn how to live more sustainable lifestyles.
7. **Engagement:** Students can become more engaged and motivated to address environmental issues.
8. **Responsible Citizens:** Students can learn to become responsible citizens who participate in environmental conservation initiatives.

Suggestions for the future Study

1. The current descriptive survey, conducted on 105 post-graduate girl students, should be replicated with a larger sample size to obtain more robust and generalizable results;
2. The study could be extended to various districts of West Bengal to explore regional differences in ecological attitudes among post-graduate female students;
3. Future research may encompass different states in India to examine interstate variations in environmental attitudes of Post-Graduate Girls;
4. The investigation can be applied to different educational levels (e.g., undergraduate or doctoral) to assess how ecological attitudes evolve with academic progression.

Limitation of the Study

1. Only 105 sample of Post Graduate students were taken for this study.
2. The research is confirmed to a specific region in West Bengal, so findings may not reflect attitudes in other districts or states.
3. Data collected from the students are all girls. Thus findings of the study cannot claim for generalizations.
4. Urban Girls Post Graduate students are less than the Rural Girls Post Graduate students. So it is not possible to get the same ratio (Urban & Rural) as sample, which may have some reflections on the responses.

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